

Toward a Sustainable Battery Future: Comparative Review of Lithium and Its Alternatives for Grid Storage

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Abstract

Lithium-ion batteries currently dominate the market for energy storage due to their high energy density, fast charge/discharge rates, and long cycle life. However, deploying them at a large grid scale is significantly hindered by very high production costs, environmental impact, and reliance on scarce raw materials. Due to these challenges, there is an increasing demand for a low-cost and environmentally friendlier alternative. The article outlines the key electrochemical properties that make lithium so uniquely effective and reviews the drawbacks that limit its large-scale viability. The existing alternatives (eg, NaIB, ZEBRA, VRFBs, etc.) are explored in terms of how they work and their electrochemical properties in comparison to LiIBs, and the unique challenges that each alternative face that makes it unviable to replace LiIBs. This review considers emerging battery technologies and future directions in grid storage. By combining the information from recent scholarly literature, this article evaluates the readiness of each technology for commercial use and explores potential directions leading to a post-LiIB storage future.

Keywords: Grid storage, Energy density, Cell voltage, SEI, ZEBRA, VRFB, Electrolyte

1. Introduction

As of 2024, over 30% of global energy generation comes from renewable sources, with solar and wind leading the growth. In countries like Germany and the UK, over 50% of electricity on the grid is from a renewable source [1], and global solar capacity alone is set to exceed 5TW by 2030. However, there is a lot of volatility caused by this transition due to solar and wind sources being intermittent due to their dependency on weather conditions, and over 5-15% of solar and wind energy has to be curtailed to maintain grid stability [2]. The mismatch between supply and demand creates fluctuations in grid frequency and voltage, making the system unreliable. Without energy storage, excess renewable energy is wasted, and fossil fuel plants must remain as a backup, creating a dependency we can't escape. Models of grids with up to 55% renewables showed that 11-16% of that energy is wasted without energy storage, while just 4 hours of battery use was able to reduce it to 8-10% [3], improving reliability and reducing the need for fossil-fuel systems.

Lithium is a soft metal at the top of group I in the periodic table, with an atomic number of 3 and an atomic mass of 6.94. A lithium atom has a single valence electron, which is easily lost, making it highly reactive. Lithium's chemical reactivity underpins its industrial and technical applications, ranging from lubricants to pharmaceuticals and, most significantly, energy storage systems. Lithium has become the cornerstone of rechargeable batteries in recent decades due to its far superior electrochemical properties compared to previous counterparts like lead. Li-Ion systems typically have a gravimetric energy density, energy stored per unit mass, of 150-250 Wh/kg, making them much more portable and convenient than previous lead-acid batteries with an energy density of 30-50 Wh/kg. Lithium also has a very high negative electrochemical potential, potential energy per unit charge in chemical reactions, due to an element's electron donation tendency. This creates a very large potential difference between the lithium anode and cathode. Due to this and the use of stable, non-aqueous electrolytes, Li-Ion cells have a high operating voltage, 3.6-4.0 V [4].

Figure 1. Comparison of voltage and capacity for insertion and conversion-type lithium battery materials, highlighting stability and energy trade-off. Reproduced with permission[4], Copyright 2017, ACS

Lithium atoms also have a tiny atomic radius of 76 pm, allowing them to move quickly through the battery and enabling intercalation, the reversible insertion of Li-ions into electrodes without damaging them. This supports rapid charge/discharge cycles and a long cycle life with minimal electrochemical degradation [5]. Despite these strengths, lithium energy storage systems face significant challenges in the context of global energy systems. Firstly, Li-Ion batteries have high upfront and operating costs, with a study reporting \$609/kWh including transport and setup costs, causing a financial burden on companies, reducing their use in grid storage [6]. Additionally, due to structural changes during charge/discharge, cracks caused by volume changes and irreversible buildup of a solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI), a thin protective layer that reduces usable lithium and accelerates degradation, Li-Ion batteries lose ~1-3 % of their capacity annually (**Figure 1**) [7]. As batteries lose capacity, they require replacement, which further increases the cost. Environmental concerns further complicate their role. Lithium extraction is very water-intensive, using over 50 meters of freshwater and 500-500,000 meters cubed of brine per ton, which has a large environmental and social impact, especially in arid regions [8].

While Li-Ion batteries enable low-carbon technologies, production of Li-Ion batteries has a very high carbon footprint, 60-110 kg CO₂ eq per kWh, much of it coming from energy-intensive mining, chemical processing, and transportation [6]. Less than 5% of Li-Ion batteries are recycled globally, and lithium used in batteries is often discarded. When kept in landfills, the batteries can leak toxic metals and electrolytes, causing long-term environmental impact [9]. As the adoption of renewable energy accelerates, the need for energy storage systems is projected to grow significantly. Due to the limitations of Li-ion batteries, the search for an affordable and reliable alternative is intensifying to ensure renewable energy systems can be integrated into all grid systems smoothly. This review explores the electrochemical and practical viability of lithium-ion alternatives for grid-scale storage. By evaluating emerging technologies, it aims to guide future research toward scalable, sustainable energy storage solutions

2. Existing alternatives

Figure 2. Structure and working of sodium-ion batteries, showing Na⁺ movement during charge/discharge and common O3 and P2 cathode types with their ion diffusion paths. Reproduced with permission[11], Copyright 2023, Springer.

Though Li-Ion batteries are the most common and dominant batteries in the market, there are many existing alternatives emerging as cost-effective, scalable, and more sustainable. Sodium-ion batteries function very similarly to Li-ion systems, utilising the

reversible intercalation of Na-ions between a carbon anode and a metal oxide cathode [10]. Sodium-sulphur systems operate at very high temperatures, where reactions of molten sodium and sulphur across a solid electrolyte are used to generate electricity [12]. Sodium-nickel chloride systems (ZEBRA) use molten sodium and nickel chloride, which are separated by a ceramic electrolyte. During discharge, sodium reacts with nickel chloride to form nickel and sodium chloride, while the reverse reaction occurs during charging. The movement of Na-ions across the ceramic electrolyte produces current [13].

Figure 3. Examples of alternative battery chemistries, including Na-metal (a–b) and Li-metal designs (c–d), showing cell structure, cycling performance, and voltage–capacity behavior. Reproduced with permission[14], Copyright 2020, ACS.

Apart from sodium, another alternative is Zinc-ion systems that work on the same principle as Na-ion and Li-ion batteries [15]. Zinc-air batteries generate electricity by utilising redox reactions, where zinc metal is oxidised at the anode and oxygen from the air is reduced at the cathode by reacting with water. OH-ions produced move across the electrolyte to the zinc anode, where electrons are released and move

through a circuit, producing current [16]. Lastly, another system is vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs). These batteries utilise the energy stored in liquid electrolytes that contain vanadium in different oxidation states. The electrolytes are pumped from external tanks through a central battery where redox reactions can occur, allowing a flow of electrons [17]. The electrochemical properties of the above alternatives are displayed in **Table 1** below, with Li-ion systems in the first row to compare.

Table 1. Table depicting the performance of batteries

Battery Type	Energy Density (Wh/kg)	Cycle Life	Efficiency (%)	Operating Temp (°C)	Cell Voltage (V)	Advantages	Ref.
Li-ion	150–250	1000–2000	~90%	15-35	3.6–3.7	Established technology, high energy density, mature supply chain	[18]
Na-ion	120-150	500-1000	~85–92%	-20 to 60	3.0-3.2	Cheaper, better low-temp performance, safer, similar voltage	[19]
Na-S	150–240	2500	~87%	~300–350	2.0-2.2	Higher energy density, lower material costs, scalable	[20]
*ZEBRA	90–120	1000-1700	80-90%	~270	2.58	Improved safety vs Na–S, moderate cost, and	[21]

						environmental impact	
*VRFB	20–35	>10,000	70–80%	15-30	1.26	Much longer cycle life, scalable for grid use, deep discharge tolerance	[17]
Zn-Air	300–400	300–1000	60–65%	Ambient	1.6 – 1.7	Extremely high theoretical energy density, low weight, and cheap materials	[22]
Zn-ion	70–120	500–2000	~75–90%	Ambient	1.65–1.80	Safe aqueous electrolytes, low-cost, recyclable, easy to integrate	[23]

*ZEBRA (Sodium nickel-chloride), VRFB (Vanadium redox flow batteries)

Figure 4. Structure of a Zn–air battery with various Zn anode forms and cathode catalyst options, highlighting gas diffusion electrode (GDE) components. Reproduced with permission[16], Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry.

3. Challenges of Existing Alternatives

Despite many advantages, existing alternatives face significant challenges that prevent them from replacing Li-ion systems.

Na-ions are much larger than Li-ions, causing them to diffuse more slowly across the electrolyte, decreasing the speed of charge/discharge cycles [24]. Furthermore, Na-ions being larger causes a greater volume change during cycles, causing electrodes to form cracks quicker, leading to faster capacity loss [25]. Additionally, Na-ions have a lower electrochemical potential, leading to a lower cell voltage and energy density. Lastly, SEI formed on sodium anodes is less stable than that on lithium anodes, causing a lower coulombic efficiency (efficiency of movement of charge) and fade in capacity [26]. Na-S batteries have low coulombic efficiency and rapid capacity loss due to the Polysulfide Shuttle Effect. This is when sodium polysulfides formed during discharge dissolve into the electrolyte, diffuse to the anode, creating a back-and-forth “shuttle” reaction. At the anode, unwanted redox reactions occur, consuming electrons, causing low coulombic efficiency, and sodium, causing rapid capacity loss even when

the circuit is not connected [27]. Also, sulphur converts to Na_2S during discharge, which causes an expansion of about 260%, leading to very large volume changes, causing electrodes to form cracks very quickly, leading to faster capacity loss [28]. Furthermore, both sulphur and Na_2S are poor electrical conductors, leading to slower reactions and charge/discharge cycles [29]. Lastly, since Na-S batteries utilise molten Na-S, they operate at 300-350 °C. At such high temperatures, there are risks of harmful sulphur vapour release and safety incidents like fires [30].

ZEBRA systems also have a very high operating temperature to keep the electrolyte NaAlCl_4 molten, increasing energy consumption and/or system complexity [31]. Additionally, the ZEBRA system has a very high material and systems cost as it requires expensive nickel cathode materials and advanced ceramics, leading to a much higher cost per kWh [32]. Furthermore, the sodium metal plating can form dendrites that pierce the ceramic electrolyte, forming shorts between the electrodes, leading to self-discharge, which reduces capacity [33].

VRFB membranes, over time, can suffer from vanadium-ion crossover, when vanadium ions pass through the membrane, causing self-discharge and reduced coulombic efficiency [34]. Additionally, the membrane also undergoes chemical degradation when exposed to vanadium. This forms pinholes, which reduces its mechanical stability over time [35]. Furthermore, the membrane, known as Nafion, is made of perfluorinated carbon chains, which are very difficult to synthesise, causing Nafion to cost \$500-700 per square meter [36]. Also, Nafion is made by very few suppliers globally and is a very niche market, so economies of scale cannot be reached yet to lower production costs. VRFBs have a low energy density (15-35 Wh/kg) due to low electrochemical potential, dilute electrolytes for stability, and heavy system components (eg, pumps, valves, tanks, etc.) that don't increase energy storage and increase mass [37]. Lastly, VRFBs are very sensitive to impurities, and even trace amounts can precipitate on electrodes, increasing resistance and reducing cycle life [38].

Zn-Air batteries have poor rechargeability due to irreversible oxygen reactions, specifically the oxygen evolution reaction (OER), which is very slow and requires a high overpotential. This makes charging the battery inefficient and reduces overall efficiency [39]. Additionally, the catalysts at the air cathode used to facilitate the

reaction degrade due to corrosion over time when exposed to high voltages. This reduces the cycle life of the battery [40]. Also, during recharge, the redeposition of zinc is uneven at the anode, which leads to the formation of dendrites that can pierce the electrolyte and cause short-circuiting. At the same time, zinc oxide passivation layers, protective layers that form to prevent corrosion, form at the anode. This increases the internal resistance of the battery and reduces performance. Furthermore, the potassium hydroxide electrolyte, which is aqueous, is vulnerable to reacting with carbon dioxide in the air to form potassium carbonate, which can clog pores in the electrodes. This reduces the conductivity of ions as they move between electrodes and leads to reduced capacity over time ([41]; [42]). Lastly, water evaporation in the aqueous electrolyte causes drying of the electrolyte. This leads to reduced ionic conductivity, reaction rates, and operational life. So, the battery requires a sealed or humidified system, which increases complexity and cost [43].

Similar to Zn-air batteries, zinc redeposition at the anode is uneven, forming dendrites, leading to short circuits [41]. Additionally, Zn-ion batteries also use aqueous electrolytes, which are prone to water evaporation, leading to reduced ion conductivity and shortened battery life [44]. Many cathode materials used in Zn-ion batteries can degrade and dissolve in the electrolytes, causing a gradual drop in capacity and very poor long-term performance [45]. Due to the use of aqueous electrolytes, at high voltages, water in the electrolyte may be reduced instead of metal ions, reducing coulombic efficiency and a build-up of hydrogen gas, which increases pressure in the battery [46]. Lastly, zinc has a lower electrochemical potential than lithium (-0.76 eV), which means Zn-ion batteries have a lower cell voltage (typically <1.9V) and a lower energy density ([47],[48]).

4. Future of Energy Storage

Though existing alternatives provide promising avenues to improve on lithium-ion systems, many new approaches are currently being researched or tested with the aim of creating more scalable, efficient, and environmentally friendly energy storage solutions.

Solid-state batteries are a promising evolution of lithium-ion technology. Instead of using flammable liquid electrolytes, these systems use solid ceramic or polymer electrolytes. This allows for significantly higher energy density, improved safety, and

longer cycle life due to the reduced risk of thermal runaway and electrolyte degradation [49]. However, solid-state systems face severe challenges such as dendrite growth through the solid electrolyte and poor interfacial contact between the electrode and electrolyte, increasing internal resistance, and reducing performance [50]. Currently, solid-state batteries are in advanced research and pilot production stages, with companies such as QuantumScape and Toyota developing prototypes for electric vehicles and portable electronics.

Quantum batteries are a theoretical jump in energy storage, using quantum mechanical systems, like entangled qubits, to store and release energy. In these systems, charging can be enhanced through quantum entanglement and coherence, allowing energy to be stored and released at speeds far exceeding current limits. Studies suggest collective quantum charging scales superlinearly with system size, a property that has not been observed in traditional batteries ([51];[52]). Quantum batteries are still at the theoretical or laboratory stage, and they have long-term potential for applications in quantum computing and nanoscale electronics, where ultra-fast energy delivery is required. Therefore, quantum batteries remain far from grid-scale application, with no practical demonstrations of scalability or long-duration storage.

Gravity-based energy storage systems work by converting excess electrical energy into gravitational potential energy by powering motors to raise heavy masses to elevated heights. When energy is needed, the masses are lowered, driving generators and producing electricity [53]. These systems don't suffer from chemical degradation and can last for decades with minimal maintenance. However, they require very large physical infrastructure, have a relatively low energy density, and are affected by mechanical inefficiencies like friction and air resistance [54]. Despite these limitations, companies like Gravitricity and Energy Vault are piloting these systems, positioning them as potential long-duration storage solutions for grid balancing.

Thermal energy storage (TES) is a non-electrochemical approach, storing electrical energy as thermal energy using materials like molten salts, concrete, or phase-change compounds. The stored thermal energy can either be used directly in industrial processes that require heating or converted back into electricity [55]. TES systems have relatively low costs and the ability to decouple energy supply from demand, but

suffer from energy conversion losses and insulation challenges at very high temperatures [56]. These systems are already in use in some concentrated solar power (CSP) plants and are being researched and tested for use in industrial decarbonisation and long-term storage.

5. Conclusions

Lithium-ion batteries currently dominate the energy storage market due to their high energy densities, long cycle lives, and high efficiencies. However, factors like cost, environmental impact, and safety risks make them unsuitable for long-term grid storage. Many alternatives have been explored, including sodium-ion, ZEBRA, VRFBs, and zinc-ion. Each of these offers significant advantages, such as lower cost or improved safety, but also has major limitations in terms of energy density, scalability, or cycle life. Some technologies, such as Na-ion and VRFBs, show promising potential in the coming years, but none currently outperform Li-ion across all key metrics. Emerging technologies like solid-state, quantum batteries, etc., may be able to overcome current limitations. However, most of these are still in the early stages in terms of research and development or scalability and will require consistent effort and funding to be considered a viable alternative.

It is unlikely that there to be a single “perfect” replacement for Li-ion batteries. Instead, the future of energy storage may consist of a diverse mix of battery technologies, all tailored to their specific applications, such as fast response or long duration. The inevitable transition to renewable energy is reliant on advances in energy storage to balance the grid, and continued research and innovation are essential to unlocking the solution. However, to meet future demands in a sustainable and resilient way, replacements for Li-ion batteries must be found.

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